

Draft Framework Outlining Innovative Evaluation Dimensions and Methods THRIVE Project (CoARA Boost, Second Cascade Funding)

Purpose: Outline alternative evaluation approaches and methods through which this transition of moving away from traditional, metric-based assessments can be carried out at an institutional level.

This document outlines a draft framework for innovative evaluation methods. These will be piloted within selected IRB recruitment processes to test efficiency and gather feedback. The ultimate goal is to foster cultural change and establish the formal documentation necessary for full-scale implementation.

1. **Narrative CVs:** With the use of Narrative CVs, candidates will have the opportunity to provide a written narrative that explains the significance and context of their key contributions. This approach will also allow the evaluators to understand the candidate's research trajectory.
2. **Top significant work:** Candidates can be asked to explain in the interview process their top one or two most significant works, along with a brief statement explaining why these works are particularly impactful and how they impacted in their trajectories. It can be a good method to encourage reflection on quality over quantity and provides evaluators with a focused set of evidence to assess scientific contribution and innovation. It also simplifies the evaluation process while highlighting meaningful achievements.
3. **Creation of a rubric to be completed during the interview:** To ensure that key information, such as professional experience, motivations, leadership roles, and broader impact, is systematically collected and considered.
4. **Proposal of recommended indicators:** Elaborate a document comprising indicators as a reference point to base the evaluations and support the implementation of responsible, qualitative, and holistic research assessment practices.
5. **Creation of guidelines:** With the aim of guide evaluators and support the way of making assessments, and in adopting qualitative assessment practices, clear and structured guidelines should be developed. The guidelines should include:
 - Principles for responsible and fair evaluation.
 - Do and don'ts for conducting interviews.
 - Recommendations for evaluating qualitative evidence.

The combination of these tools and methods is designed to foster a culture of reflection, fairness, and holistic evaluation, allowing institutions to move away from purely metric-driven assessments toward approaches that capture the full scope of a candidate's contributions and potential.